

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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MUNDARIJA

Uy-joy qurilishi madaniyati, uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va tamoyillari.....	10
Davletov Islambek Xalikovich, Zikrullayev Valixon G'aybulla o'g'li	
Hududlar investitsiya muhitini oshirish muammolari.....	16
Akbarov Bekmurod Miryakubovich	
Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasi ellikqal'a tumanida turizm klasterini joriy qilish mexanizmi.....	22
Norchayev Asatullo Norbo'tayevich	
Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship is the Priority Direction of Our Country's Economy.....	28
Tulagan Tukhtaraliev, G'aniev Muhammadjon Xalilovich	
Resurs soliqlarini soliqqa tortish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish.....	31
Tursunova Zulayxo Abdujobir qizi	
O'zbekistonda muqobil energiya manbalaridan foydalanish elektrotexnika sanoati rivojlanishining istiqboli sifatida.....	34
Uraimjonov Azizbek Raxmonjon o'g'li	
Oliy ta'limning raqobatbardoshligini ta'minlashda ta'lim sifatining mohiyati va asosiy tamoyillari (O'zbekiston misolida).....	40
Egamov Sevinchbek Maxsud o'g'li	
Financial Mechanisms of Supporting Textile Products Export.....	46
Gaybullayeva Gulbaxor Maxmudovna, Yakubova Ugiloy Mamasoliyevna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida hududlarni mutanosib barqaror rivojlantirish masalalari va yechimlari.....	49
Hojiyev Tal'at Toshpo'latovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida ayollar biznesini shakllantirish yo'llari.....	54
Ibodullayeva Malohat Sirojiddin qizi	
Davlatning iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi.....	57
Bekmirzayev Mirzoxid Adashaliyevich	
Turizm sohasi rivojlanishining istiqbollari.....	61
Ergashev Rahmatulla Xidirovich, Jabborova Zuhra Abdig'ani qizi	
Jahonda kabel bozorini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari va tendensiyalari.....	68
Uralov Olimjon Mahammadjonovich	
Namangan viloyatida yoshlarning iqtisodiy faolligi ko'rsatkichlari dinamikasini tahlil qilish.....	72
Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	
Turizm sohasiga malakali kadrlar tayyorlashdagi muammolar va ularning yechimlari borasida tavsiyalar.....	77
A. I. Raxmatov	
Трансформация внешнеторговых связей Республики Узбекистана.....	83
Ахмедова (Жабборова) Нилуфар Икболжон кизи	
Korxonalarda investitsiyalarni moliyalashtirish manbalari va usullarining tahlili.....	88
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Turizmning mohiyati xususida nazariy yondoshuvlar va ularning tahlili.....	94
R. I. Pardayev	
Katta hajmga ega bo'lgan maxsus qurtxonalarda boqilayotgan ipak qurtlariga harorat va namlikni ta'siri.....	101
Raxmanova Xurinisho Egamovna	
Mahalliy byudjet daromadlarini shakllantirishda mahalliy soliqlar va soliqdan tashqari tushumlarning ahamiyati.....	104
Rajjaboyeva Dildora Zakirovna	
Banklarda stress-test asosida ESG-risklarni baholash.....	110
Nilufar Sharipova	
Yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda banklarda ekologik va ijtimoiy risklarni baholash va boshqarish tizimini joriy etishning ahamiyati.....	114
Karimov Shamsiddin Akram o'g'li	

Qimmatli qog'ozlarni qiymatini baholash usullari va modellari.....	122
Botirxo'ja Aziza Faxmuddin qizi	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarishda diversifikatsiyaning nazariy asoslari.....	127
Davronbek Sharibjonovich Raximov	
Mamlakatimizda innovatsiyalarni moliyalashtirishning amaldagi holati tahlili.....	133
Aminov Farrux Farxadovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda moliyaviy hisobot tahlilini takomillashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	138
G. J. Jumayeva	
Qurilish sohasida logistika tizimlariga zamonaviy texnologiyalar bilan ta'minlanganlarning amaliy jihatlari....	141
Mirsodiqov Abdulla Tursunaliyevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida inson kapitalini boshqarishdagi muammolar	146
Nematova Shaxlo Egamberdiyevna	
Aholi daromdlari va omonatlarini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	149
Xakimov Zohid Norbo'tayevich	
Tasvirlarga raqamli ishlov berish jarayonini intellektualashtirish algoritmini yaratish.....	158
Zoirov O'lmas Erkin o'g'li	
Mintaqa iqtisodiyotida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyalashtirish samaradorligini baholash	164
Chilmatova Dilnoza Abdurahimovna	
Возможности внедрения и развития исламских банковских продуктов в рынок Узбекистана.....	168
Иноятова Камола Фуркатовна	
Davlat xizmatchisi faoliyatida ijtimoiy javobgarlikning o'rni	172
X. X. Ikramov	
Korporativ boshqaruv tizimida buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	176
Abdug'aniyev Muhammadamin Abdug'affor o'g'li	
Hududiy kambag'allik chegaralarini aniqlashning ahamiyati (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida).....	182
Hamdamov Shahzod Ilhom o'g'li, Alisher Yunusaliyevich Safarov	
Kichik biznesga mahalliy investitsiyalarni jalb qilish va ulardan samarali foydalanishda franshizaning roli	189
Rabimqulov Sherzod Murtozayevich	
Tijorat banklarida marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	193
Maxamadjanov Akbar Maxamadaliyevich	
Davlat sherikchilik asosida maktab va maktabgacha ta'lim moliyashtirishligini o'ziga xos xususiyatligi.....	198
Boltaboev Murodbek Aybekovich	
Moliyaviy savodxonlikni rivojlantirish davr talabi.....	203
X. I. Boyev	
Banklarda chakana kreditlash turlari va ularni raqamli transformatsiya qilishning zarurligi.....	207
Axmedova Dilrabo Kurbondurdi qizi	
Rasmiy ish bilan bandlik – aholining munosib turmush darajasini ta'minlash demak.....	216
Farhod Bagibekovich Xalimbetov	
Jismoniy shaxslardan olinadigan daromad solig'i uchun qo'llaniladigan soliq imtiyozlarining amaldagi holati va tahlili.....	220
Valiyeva Sayyora Xushbaqovna	
Автомобильная промышленности развитых стран: становление, развитие, пути совершенствования.....	227
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Абдухамидова Мафтуна Турсуналт кизи	
Влияние цифровизации на внешнеэкономическую деятельность	232
Шермаматова Ирода Ойбековна, Тиллаев Хуршиджон Сулаймон ўгли	
ИИ в банковском бизнесе: ключ к конкурентной привлекательности	238
Фаттахова Муниса Абдухамитовна	
Tijorat banklari kapitalining iqtisodiy mazmuni va uning tarkibi	243
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	

Особенности банковского кредитования и факторы препятствующие финансово-кредитной поддержке субъектов сферы туристических услуг	248
Розоков Мухаммадазиз Мансурович	
Factoring Operations in Banks.....	253
Boykabilova Iroda, Davronova Dilnoza Damirovna	
Moliyaviy sektordagi aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining korporativ strategiyasini shakllantirishda risklarni bartaraf etish.....	257
Jaxongirov Rustam Jaxongirovich, Xo'jamurodov Asqarjon Jalolovich	
O'zbekistonning jozibador investitsiya muhitini yaratishda huquqiy asoslarni yanada takomillashtirishning ilmiy va amaliy zaruriyati	264
Oybek Elmuratov	
Qurilish materiallarini ishlab chiqarish korxonalarining boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	268
Uzakova Umida Ruzievna	
Tashkent Economy – Locomotive of the Country's Economy	274
Akramova Aziza Abduvohidovna, Maqsudov Bunyod Abdusamadovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida ishbilarmonlik turizmining tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	278
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilhomovna	
Mintaqalar iqtisodiyotining barqaror o'sishini ta'minlashda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish mezonlari va ularni hisoblash usullari	284
Norqobilov Nusrat Norsaitovich	
Marketing strategiyasi: raqobatchilik sharoitida tadbirkorlik faoliyatini yuritishning rivojlantirilishi	288
Kutbitdinova Moxigul Inoyatovna, Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusubayevna	
Mahalliy budjetlar mablag'laridan samarali foydalanishni ta'minlashning eng asosiy istiqbolli yo'nalishi	295
S. Y. Ismoilova	
Atrof-muhitga zararsiz, tabiiy tarkibli korroziya ingibitorlari turlarini tahlil qilish	300
Qurbonova Furuza Solexovna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida xarajatlar smetalari ijrosi hisobini yuritish tartibi	306
AbdulAziz Norqo'chqorov Ziyadullayevich	
Tijorat banklarining investitsion faoliyati samaradorligi va uni rivojlantirish yo'llari	312
Olimova Nodira Xamrakulovna	
Baholangan majburiyatlar hisobini takomillashtirish.....	324
Ochilov Farxodjon Shavkatjon o'g'li	
Qurilish-pudrat tashkilotlarida auditorlik tekshiruvda faoliyat uzluksizligini baholash.....	331
Tulovov Erkinjon To'liqin o'g'li	
Основные направления развития инвестиционной деятельности предприятий.....	335
Махкамова Надира Саидмуратовна	
Milliy statistika axborot tizimlarining funksional jihatlari va o'ziga xos xususiyatlarining tahlili	340
Otajonova Gulhayo Maqsud qizi	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlik faoliyatini boshqarish axborot tizimini modellashtirish	345
Xudoyorov Laziz Niyozovich, Ergashova Nargiza Boboxonovna	
Mamlakatimizda aksiz to'lanadigan tovarlarni soliqqa tortish usullari	351
Alimardonov Muxammadi Ibragimovich, Qarshiyev Daniyar Eshpulatovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish sharoitida investitsiya loyihalarini jalb qilgan mablag'lar orqali moliyalashtirishning zarurligi.....	357
Amonova Dilafroz O'tkurovna	
To'lov tashkilotlarini tashkil etishda xatarlarni boshqarish	362
Axmedov Miraziz Alisherovich	
Korxonada inson kapitalini rivojlantirish tizimi va konsepsiyasini takomillashtirish imkoniyatlari	367
Hamrokulov M. O.	

Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida kichik sanoat zonalarini faoliyatining zarurligi va iqtisodiy-huquqiy maqomi.....	375
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
Bank tizimida marketing faoliyati orqali yangi innovatsion xizmatlarni joriy etishning zamonaviy holati.....	379
Raxmatov Temur Sotiboldiyevich	
Экономическая сущность инновационной деятельности в банковском секторе	388
Шадиева Дилдора Хамидовна	
Yengil sanoat taraqqiyotining xitoy tajribasi va undan o'zbekistonda foydalanish imkoniyatlari	392
Jumaniyazova Feruza Rajabovna	
Tut parvonasi zararkunandasing biologik tarqalishi va zararini oldini olish choralari.....	402
Oybek Toshemirovich Karimov	
Ijtimoiy adolat va ayollar huquqlari: kasbiy kamsitish	406
Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna	
Ishsizlik nafaqalari tayinlash va xalqaro tajriba.....	412
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Takroriy ekinlar urug'ini to'g'ridan-to'g'ri nol ishlov berish orqali ekadigan qurilmaga tushadigan yuklamaning nazariy tadqiqoti.....	418
Abdullayev Baxodirjon Valijon o'g'li	
Banklarida jinoiy faoliyatdan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirishga qarshi kurashish tizimining roli.....	422
Abdullayeva Dildora Quدراتovna	
Biologik aktivlar hisobini moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartari asosida tashkil etishning uslubiy jihatlari	425
Adxamov Samariddin	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishga erishishda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarning ahamiyati.....	430
Asqarova Mavluda Turabovna, Otajonova Charosxon Polvonquli qizi	
Ilmiy-innovatsion iqtisodiyotda suv xo'jaligini rivojlantirish muammolari, yechimlar va natijalar: fundamental asosda.....	435
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Budjet tashkilotlarida buxgalteriya hisobini yuritishning milliy va xalqaro standartlari.....	441
Maxamadaliyeva Mahliyoqon Maxamadmurod qizi	
Tijorat banklari aktivlari va ularni samarali boshqarish nazariy asoslari.....	448
Masharipov Maxmud Bekturdiyevich	
Tijorat banklarning moliyaviy faoliyatida yuzaga keladigan xavf-xatar va uning mohiyati	453
Rashidov Raximjon Iskandarovich, Abduraxmonov Anvar Akbar o'g'li	
Kichik sanoat zonalarini barpo etish va rivojlantirish omillari va hozirgi holatining tahlili	459
Samijonov Musobek G'ayratjon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy menejment tizimi samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli marketing strategiyasidan foydalanish	466
Sobirjonov Sanjar Sobirjonovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliyaviy tizimida byudjetdan tashqari jamg'armalarning ahamiyati va o'rni.....	473
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Babanazarova Gulzar Ziuatdinovna, Ajibayeva Raiya Maxsudovna	
Aholi daromadlarini oshirishda asalarichilikning o'rni	479
Xudayarova Zuxra Yuldashevna	
Цифровые и традиционные методы сбора информации в маркетинговых исследованиях: сравнительный анализ.....	482
Бекназова Комилахон Миркамол қизи	
Tijorat banklari faoliyatida iqtisodiy risklar va ularni nazariy asoslari.....	490
Burxonov Asliddin Asqar o'g'li	
Biznes tuzilmalarini diversifikatsiya qilish modellari va usullari hamda innovatsion rivojlanish strategiyalarining qiyosiy tavsifi.....	497
Matyoqubova Dilfuza Olimboyevna	

Тенденции развития пищевой промышленности Узбекистана.....	503
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Нигматуллаева Гульчехра Нуруллаевна	
Soliq-bojxona siyosatining dolzarb masalalari va ularni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	509
Usmonov Kaxramonjon Akbaraliyevich	
Статистический анализ факторов, влияющих на бренд молока и молочных продуктов в Узбекистане	513
Холдарова Фариза Тухтабаевна	
Правовое регулирование рынка цифровых активов и криптовалют.....	519
Якубова Ш. Ш., Рашидов Рахимжон Искандарович	
Efficiency of Internal Audit Service and Report Improvement: Control of Sanatorium-Wellness Institution	528
Shafkarov Fahriddin Khudaiberdievich	
Development of Digital TV Services in the Conditions of Digitalization of the Economy.....	534
Farhad Karimov	
Kichik biznes faoliyatida muhim muvaffaqiyat omillarini belgilashning ahamiyati va ularni baholash.....	538
Kabulova Nurgo'zal Umirbek qizi	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ekonometrik tadqiq etish.....	541
Muminova Maxbuba Abduvafoyevna	
Korxonaning moliyaviy-xo'jalik faoliyati ko'rsatkichlarini baholash.....	548
Musurmonova Mahbuba Omonovna	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari tashqi savdo faoliyatini ichki tartibga solishni takomillashtirishning ayrim jihatlari..	552
To'rayev Nurbek Muxammadovich	
Temir yo'l transportida xizmat ko'rsatish jarayonini rivojlantirishning retseptiv tahlili.....	557
Raxmonov G'ayrat Ismatulloevich	
Strategik boshqaruv hisobi va uning uslubiyotini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	562
Sharipova Shoxida Abdinabiyevna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida "yashil" iqtisodiyotni qo'llab-quvvatlashning iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	567
Shodmonov Ruslan G'olib o'g'li	
Institutsional investorlar faoliyatini tashkil etishning kontseptual jihatlari	574
Sultanov Maxmud Axmedovich	
Tijorat banklari foydasini soliqqa tortishning ayrim me'yoriy-huquqiy asoslari.....	578
Turanov M. Sh.	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishida tijorat banklarining o'rni.....	586
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Babanazarova Gulzar Ziuatdinovna, Zubaydullayeva Zulayxo Karimovna, Kaxarova Dildora Erkinovna	
O'zbekistonda tayyor kiyimlar bozori ko'lamini oshirishda marketing strategiyalarining samaradorligi.....	596
Urazov Mansur Musurmanovich	
Yevropaga barqaror eksport va qishloq xo'jaligida yashil rivojlanish uchun Mosh bozori strategiyalarining ta'sirini baholash	599
Valiyeva Aziza Anvar qizi	
Rangli tasvirlarga raqamli ishlov berish jarayonlarini paralellashtirish	605
Xidirova Barchinoy Ilxomovna	
Korxonalarda ishchi personal ehtiyojlarini motivatsiyaga ta'siri	610
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich, Axmedov Muzaffar Shokirjonovich	
Цифровые и традиционные методы сбора информации в маркетинговых исследованиях: сравнительный анализ	615
Бекназова Комилахон Миркамол қизи	
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....	623
Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	
Positioning Textile Products in Competitive Strategy.....	626
Икрамова Нодира Бурхон қизи	

Sanoatni tarkibiy o'zgarishlar asosida maqbullashtirish va samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarini prognozlash.....	631
Kasimov Azamat Abdukarimovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi budgetini shakllanishida egri soliqlarni undirishning fiskal samaradorligi	638
Abdulxayeva Shahnoza Muxammadiyevna	
To'qimachilik klasterlari eksport salohiyatini boshqarish masalalari.....	645
Mamasoliyev G'ayratbek Maxamadyusupovich	
Влияние плодородности почвы на урожайность хлопчатника в хлопково-текстильных кластерах Республики Каракалпакстан	650
Сагиева Молдир Оразбай кизи	

POSITIONING TEXTILE PRODUCTS IN COMPETITIVE STRATEGY

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Abstract: In the competitive situation in the market, positioning is of great importance in the textile industry. For example, a brand can position itself as a manufacturer of high-quality and environmentally friendly materials, attracting customers who value environmental friendliness and durability of products. Another brand may focus on affordable prices and a wide selection, attracting customers interested in low prices. Each approach creates a unique position in the market and determines the specific needs of the target audience.

Key words: competitive strategy, brand position, environmentally friendly, recyclable materials.

Annotatsiya: Bozordagi raqobat sharoitida to'qimachilik sanoatida pozitsiyalashni aniqlash katta ahamiyatga ega. Misol uchun, brend o'zini yuqori sifatli va ekologik toza materiallar ishlab chiqaruvchisi sifatida ko'rsatishi mumkin, mahsulotning ekologik tozaligi va chidamliligini qadrlaydigan mijozlarni jalb qiladi. Boshqa brend arzon narxlarga qiziqqan mijozlarni jalb qilib, arzon narxlar va keng tanlovga e'tibor qaratishi mumkin. Har bir yondashuv bozorda o'ziga xos mavqeni yaratadi va maqsadli auditoriyaning o'ziga xos ehtiyojlarini belgilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqobat strategiyasi, brend pozitsiyasi, ekologik toza, qayta ishlanadigan materiallar.

Аннотация: В условиях конкурентной ситуации на рынке большое значение в текстильной отрасли имеет позиционирование. Например, бренд может позиционировать себя как производитель качественных и экологически чистых материалов, привлекая клиентов, ценящих экологичность и долговечность продукции. Другой бренд может сделать акцент на доступных ценах и широком выборе, привлекая клиентов, заинтересованных в низких ценах. Каждый подход создает уникальную позицию на рынке и определяет конкретные потребности целевой аудитории.

Ключевые слова: конкурентная стратегия, позиция бренда, экологичность, вторсырье.

INTRODUCTION

In the world of textiles, competitive success depends not only on skill, but also on a strategic approach to determining the position of products in the market. Correct positioning helps firms to stand out among many players and create sustainable competitive advantages for your brand.

Product positioning is the art of identifying a product or service's place in the minds of consumers, creating a unique image and expressing brand values through every element of the product. This process involves analyzing the target audience, identifying competitive advantages, and creating a connection between the brand and consumers.

A key element of successful positioning is understanding the needs and preferences of the target audience. Adapting products and marketing strategies to consumer needs ensures maximum relevance and appeal to the target audience.

However, for successful positioning it is necessary not only to understand the needs of the market, but also to be able to stand out among competitors. Creating a unique offering based on innovative design, high-quality materials, environmentally sustainable manufacturing or unique marketing strategies will help capture the attention and interest of consumers.

Positioning also includes creating a strong brand and creating an emotional connection with consumers. Branding plays an important role in creating a unique identifier for a product, making it easier to recognize and associate with the brand.

Thus, positioning textile products in a competitive strategy is a complex and multi-level process that requires a deep understanding of market conditions, consumer needs and the ability to differ from competitors.

Only this approach will allow companies to create a unique offer that can win the choice of consumers and ensure the sustainable success of the brand.

METHODOLOGY

The research of the article on the topic of positioning textile products within the framework of competitive strategy is based on the following stages:

- **Determination of the goals and objectives of the study:** scientific substantiation and development of methods for positioning goods in the textile industry by light industry enterprises of different countries.
- **Object of study:** positioning of goods of textile industry enterprises and a brief comparison with western and eastern textile giants.
- **Subject of research:** methodological support for the positioning of goods in the textile industry.
- **Theoretical basis of the study:** development of the theory of product positioning and development of methodological approaches to its implementation.
- **Development of methods:**
 - methodology for assessing the competitive position of goods from the point of view of consumers;
 - methodology for selecting attributes for positioning textile products;
 - mechanism for positioning goods by enterprises of the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Scientific novelty of the results: development of the theoretical basis for product positioning and development of methodological approaches to its implementation.

RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS

Positioning textile products within a competitive strategy is a strategic process that involves identifying the unique features of the product, identifying the target audience and creating an appropriate brand image to attract attention in the market and achieve competitive advantage. In this study, we will explore the key aspects of textile product positioning and their impact on the competitive strategy of companies in this industry.

First of all, textile product positioning begins with an analysis of the market and competitive environment. Companies must study consumer preferences and needs, as well as analyze the actions of competitors. This will help identify open niches in the market and develop a strategy that will allow the company to stand out.

An important aspect of positioning is identifying the target audience. Companies need to understand who their key customers are and what needs they have. For example, clothing for young people may have a different style and price range than clothing for older people. Positioning must be tailored to the interests and preferences of the target audience. Then it is necessary to determine the unique features of the products that will help the company stand out in the market. This could be the use of environmentally friendly materials, innovative design, high quality or affordable price. For example, a company may position itself as a brand that offers fashionable organic cotton clothing at affordable prices.

In addition, it is important to create an appropriate brand image that will correspond to the values and preferences of the target audience. This includes creating a unique style, logo, packaging and marketing materials that will help the brand stand out and be remembered by consumers.

Research has identified two methods of product positioning: the first is based on consumer perception of the product, the second is based on comparison with competitors, taking into account their advantages. However, these methods do not take into account factors influencing customer preferences (expectations, needs, income, age, product knowledge and satisfaction), which makes successful product positioning difficult. The thesis recommends an integrated approach to positioning.

Table 1: An integrated approach to product positioning

The next level of creating a distinguishing characteristic of a product, establishing its position in the market comes with finding special attributes or features that allow firms to differ from others. The methodology for selecting attributes of a product position allows companies to determine the product characteristics, on the basis of which an enterprise can create its positions in consumer perception.

Table 2: Methodology for selecting product positioning attributes

The application of this methodology includes the following aspects:

Classification of attributes to determine product positioning, including product attributes (quality, market, service attributes) and consumer characteristics (needs, demographic, psychographic, behavioral, economic characteristics).

Segmentation of consumers based on the sought benefits corresponding to the motives their behavior.

Assessing the use by competitors of the attributes underlying the positioning of their goods, using a developed methodology for assessing the competitive positioning of goods in the perception of consumers.

Assessing the compliance of goods of competing enterprises with consumer expectations based on the ideal point model, which allows us to identify the causes of consumer dissatisfaction and develop recommendations for improvement of the product.

Selection of product attributes based on the following conditions: the attribute is significant for consumers; a significant attribute is not used by competitors when positioning their products; if a significant attribute is used by competitors, it can be selected in case of weak positions occupied by them; If competitors' positions are assessed as strong and they use a significant attribute, it may be selected if there is an opportunity to improve the product, which provides superiority over competitors.

Sustainability is also becoming an important aspect of positioning textile products in the modern world. As consumer awareness of environmental issues increases, companies offering products made from recycled materials or with sustainability in mind can gain a strong position in the market.

However, positioning must take into account not only consumer preferences and needs, but also the actions of competitors. Competition in the textile industry can be fierce, and companies must constantly monitor changes in the market and adapt their strategies in accordance with these changes. Thus, positioning textile products within a competitive strategy is a complex and multi-level process that requires market analysis, identification of target audience, highlighting the unique features of products and forming an appropriate brand image. Companies that successfully apply positioning can achieve competitive advantages and become leaders in the textile market.

A historical overview of the development of the textile industry in Western and Eastern countries shows how the industry has transformed over time and what differences exist in approaches and strategies between different cultures and regions. In Western countries, the textile industry went through a process of industrialization in the 19th century, leading to massive production of clothing and textiles. An example of a successful company of that time is Levi Strauss & Co., founded in 1853 in the USA. Levi Strauss became one of the largest manufacturers of jeans and other clothing that became a symbol of the American way of life.

Eastern countries such as China and India had a rich history of textile production long before industrialization in the West. China, for example, has been a center of silk production for centuries, facilitating the development of sericulture and the silk trade. Today, China is the world's largest exporter of textile goods and a leading producer of synthetic fibers.

Current trends in the textile industry reflect the influence of globalization, innovation and sustainable development. Western companies such as Nike and Adidas are actively introducing new technologies and materials into the production of sportswear and footwear. For example, Nike develops and uses various types of synthetic fibers and fabrics to create lightweight and durable sports products. However, sustainable production is becoming an increasingly important aspect of the textile industry. Companies are striving to reduce their environmental impact by using recyclable materials and improving production processes. Patagonia is known for its efforts to produce sustainably and create fair working conditions for its employees. Comparing the development of the textile industry in the West and East allows us to understand differences in historical approaches and cultural influences, as well as identify common trends that shape the industry today.

Table 3: Examples of brands using recyclable materials

Brand	Examples of recyclable materials
Patagonia	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, recycled nylon
Adidas	Recycled polyester, recycled nylon, recycled elastane.
Stella McCartney	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, forest-sourced viscose.
Eileen Fisher	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, recycled cashmere, recycled nylon.
Reformation	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, forest-sourced viscose, tencel.
Outerknown	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, recycled nylon, tencel, BCI cotton.
Nudie Jeans	Organic cotton, recycled polyester.
Everlane	Organic cotton, recycled polyester.
Thought Clothing	Organic cotton, bamboo, forest-sourced rayon, hemp, recycled polyester.
Knowledge Cotton App.	Organic cotton, recycled polyester, forest-sourced viscose, tencel.

These companies are just a few of those that use recycled materials in their products. Their experience shows the possibilities and importance of using environmentally friendly materials in the textile industry.

Uzbekistan has established itself in the global textile industry thanks to its rich traditions of textile production, excellent quality of natural materials such as cotton and silk, and attractive prices. This provides the country with competitiveness in the international arena and attracts the attention of consumers who are looking for high-quality textile products at a reasonable cost. Uzbek brands should use environmentally friendly materials to produce clothing, as this reduces the negative impact on the environment. Organic cotton, bamboo and lyocell reduce the consumption of non-renewable resources and reduce emissions of harmful substances. It is also important to recycle waste and encourage conscious consumption among consumers.

CONCLUSION

As was depicted above, there are many ways for companies and the countries' textile industries to position themselves in the global competitive arena.

Some companies might choose to follow the interests and preferences of the target audience while others are concentrating more on the environmental image of a brand.

Another conclusion is about the cost of the production and its impact on the price formation; hence this fact is directly linked to the affordability of a product. Making products at a lower price is also a type of a widely used brand positioning in the textile industry. Namely, Uzbek companies are known to be cheap textile producers of stockinet and knitwear.

All in all, positioning textile products within a competitive strategy is a complex and multi-level process that requires market analysis, identification of target audience, highlighting the unique features of products and forming an appropriate brand image.

An integrated approach to product positioning is one of the key elements in the market positioning which incorporates the purpose of positioning is to create strong position of the product by shaping the necessary perceptions and preferences of target consumers.

Another important factor is analyzing the competitors' products and their attributes to make a successful positioning of the brand in the competitive market.

One more option that has become widespread due to popularization of Green Economy is making products recyclable or to manufacture items from recycled materials, a lot of firms are currently utilizing this method to create special value in the customers' minds.

List of References:

1. Belyaev V.I. Marketing: fundamentals of theory and practice: textbook. – M.: KNORUS, 2005. –672 p.
2. Pankrukhin A.P. Marketing: Textbook. — 3rd ed. – M.: Omega-L, 2005. –656 p.
3. Kotler F. Marketing management. – St. Petersburg: Peter, 2000.
4. Osipenko N.A., "Методическое обеспечение позиционирования товаров текстильной промышленности на рынке Республики Беларусь" Belarus State Economic University, Minsk, 2018.
5. Ivang R., Rana M.B. Better World Fashion: Circular Economy and Competitive Advantage. Ivey Publishing, 2019, 16 p.
6. Thind R. Strategic Fashion Management: Concepts, Models and Strategies for Competitive Advantage. London, Routledge, 2017, 182 p. URL: Link.
7. Lewis B., Hawksley A. Gaining a Competitive Advantage in Fashion Retailing. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management, 1990, vol. 18, iss. 4.
8. Khvorostyanaya A.S. Fashion industry strategizing: theory and practice. St. Petersburg: SZIU RANEPА, 2021. 272 p.
9. Novikova I.V. Strategic management of enterprise labor resources // Economics in industry. 2018. T. 11. No. 4. pp. 318–326.
10. Kvint V.L. Theory and practice of strategizing. Tashkent: Tasvir, 2018. 160 p.
11. Kvint V.L. Strategy for the Global Market: Theory and Practical applications. New York, Routledge, 2015, 548 p.
12. Khvorostyanaya A.S. Using the methodology of financial strategy in asset management of the creative economy // Economics and Management. 2017. No. 8. pp. 67–74.
13. Porter M.E. The Five Competitive Forces that Shape Strategy. Harvard Business Review, 2008, vol. 86, iss. 1, pp. 78–93.
14. Porter M. Competitive advantage: How to achieve high results and ensure its sustainability. M.: Alpina Publisher, 2008. 720 p.
15. Kotler Ph. From Sales Obsession to Marketing Effectiveness. Harvard Business Review, 1997, no. 55, pp. 67–75.
16. Kapferer J.-N. The New Strategic Brand Management: Creating and Sustaining Brand Equity Long Term. Kogan Page Publishers, 2008, 560 p.
17. Kotler F., Jain D.K., Masinsey S. Marketing maneuvers. Modern approaches to profit, growth and renewal.

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